
Research Proposal

Culturally Competent Classrooms: Embracing Culturally Responsive Pedagogy in STEM Education through Design-Based Approach

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Abstract

This design-based research project examines how culturally responsive pedagogy can be effectively integrated into higher education STEM classrooms at a large Hispanic-serving institution in the United States. Despite serving diverse student populations, STEM departments at the institution lack guidance, training, and curricular structures to support culturally responsive teaching. Guided by stakeholder interviews and existing literature, the study seeks to develop and refine a scalable model of culturally responsive pedagogy that incorporates culturally relevant course content, inclusive assessments, faculty development, and opportunities for student voice. Using conjecture mapping to link design elements, mediating processes, and desired outcomes, the project explores the challenges and opportunities of implementation and investigates how these practices influence student engagement, success, and retention in STEM fields. The long-term goal is to support sustainable institutional change that fosters equitable and culturally responsive STEM learning environments.

Keywords

culturally responsive pedagogy, STEM education, design-based research, inclusive teaching, student engagement, higher education

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Introduction

The following research study aims to create a design-based research approach project to explore the approaches to embracing culturally responsive pedagogy in STEM Education. This project emerged as a need to address the current existing status quo across many departments at institutions of higher learning. Through the lack of implementing culturally responsive content to be mandatory in its STEM courses, institutions might ignore a crucial need for students and faculty to engage with culturally engaging content to improve engagement and retention (Adetunji et al., 2023; Stein et al., 2024). The fact that STEM departments serve a large minoritized student population with often low retention rates guides this research to shed light on the complexities and challenges related to the culturally responsive curriculum in the higher education STEM classroom while implementing theory to practice through this design-based research project.

Based on the current literature on the topic along with qualitative data gathered from the subjects, it is possible to implement a general model of culturally responsive pedagogy across the STEM departments at institutions of higher learning that is broad enough to provide faculty with sufficient autonomy over the content taught. Through data gathered in this study, I aim to provide faculty and departments with a model to implement in STEM classrooms' curricula. The model would facilitate the incorporation of culturally responsive pedagogy in the classrooms and can be utilized across all STEM disciplines. The following are the questions guiding my research: *1) In what ways can culturally responsive teaching practices be integrated into higher education STEM classrooms to support diverse populations? 2) What are the challenges and opportunities for implementing culturally responsive pedagogy in the higher education STEM classroom? 3) How does implementing these impact student engagement success and retention in STEM fields?*

Key Issues

One of the major issues that is currently preventing faculty from the widespread implementation of culturally responsive practices and curricula in their classrooms is the lack of direction from the departments that would be equipped with resources to facilitate this implementation. This factor is additionally enforced by the lack of a requirement for the implementation of culturally responsive approaches to teaching (Págan, 2022). These factors affect the faculty who are perhaps new to teaching and those responsible for educating the majority-minoritized and multicultural student populations in their classrooms. According to the existing research on the topic, a lack of culturally relevant course content affects student engagement and retention (Hammond, 2014; Davis et al., 2023). In fact, creating course content that is more relevant to student experiences can increase student engagement and success in the classroom. This issue might be even more prevalent in online classrooms, where course design is proven to be the third

most common reason why students drop out of an open online education program (Greenland & Moore, 2021).

The issues mentioned above not only impact success in the classroom but also have an impact on the instructors. Since the integration of culturally relevant approaches to content and instruction is not required by the departments, implementing such in teaching ultimately falls on the shoulders of the instructors, which often translates into invisible labor that goes beyond the role expectations (Gordon et al., 2022).

Contextual Factors and Researcher Positionality

To learn about the possible avenues for research and existing research gaps, I conducted semi-structured interviews with the stakeholders. The information and stories that were shared with me helped me understand the *big picture* of the issues related to STEM classrooms and the gaps that exist in terms of student and faculty support. The semi-structured nature of the interviews allowed me to build a certain level of rapport with the participants, which helped in creating a more authentic conversation on the topic of culturally responsive practices in STEM classrooms.

To provide a viable solution to the existing issue, it is important to understand the contextual factors that influence the existing status quo at institutions. First, the institutional size often adds more difficulty in terms of streamlining curriculum efforts, as there are multiple layers to executing and implementing final policies. Conversely to that, the lack of clear directions given by the departments gives instructors the autonomy to design their own culturally responsive courses; nonetheless, this activity is often laborious for the university faculty and instructors are often not recognized for their efforts to support students. Another issue that aids the context is the lack of faculty training and resources due to constraining financial obligations of institutions. According to the stakeholders, the incoming faculty does not receive training on diversifying their curricula to implement culturally responsive content. On the other hand, it is important to mention that the existing faculty and stakeholders might be *resistant to change*. This barrier is also applicable to the departmental context. The resistance to change hinders efforts to implement new practices, as certain educators and stakeholders might be skeptical or apprehensive about the new approaches to teaching and learning. Moreover, the new approaches to teaching in a more culturally responsive manner (eg. incorporating social media in the lecture content and learning activities, pop culture references, utilizing technology in the classroom) might conflict with the traditional perspectives on teaching and learning.

As a researcher, it is important to acknowledge my positionality concerning the above-mentioned contextual factors. As a doctoral student studying higher education, I am mindful of the limitations that exist in terms of institutional resources. Therefore, my project will provide a

solution for instructors and departments can utilize that will not require additional monetary efforts.

Figure 1. Contextual Factors: Systemic and Situational Challenges and Barriers

Opportunities for Working Together to Create Culturally Responsive Classrooms

In order to create a plan for a culturally responsive curriculum model, I will first provide a conjecture map to portray the design relationships and research goals. A conjecture map is a foundational tool in design-based research that makes explicit the theoretical assumptions underlying the intervention and helps visualize the connections between the design features, mediating processes, and desired outcomes (Sandoval, 2014). This visual representation serves multiple purposes: it articulates the researcher's hypotheses about how the design will work, provides a framework for data collection and analysis, and allows for iterative refinement as the research progresses (Severance et al., 2016).

The conjecture map for this project illustrates the relationship between three critical components: design elements (the specific features of the culturally responsive pedagogy model), mediating processes (the mechanisms through which these features are expected to work), and outcomes (the anticipated changes in instructor practice and student success). By mapping these relationships explicitly, the conjecture map serves as both a planning tool and a hypothesis-testing framework throughout the design-based research process (McKenney & Reeves, 2019).

Design Elements: The "What"

The design elements represent the tangible components of the culturally responsive pedagogy model that will be introduced into STEM classrooms. Based on the literature and stakeholder interviews, these elements include:

1. **Culturally relevant course content:** Integration of examples, case studies, and problem sets that reflect the diverse cultural backgrounds and experiences of students in the classroom (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). For instance, in a biology course, this might involve discussing genetic research that has implications for Hispanic health disparities, or in engineering, examining infrastructure challenges in students' home countries or communities.
2. **Faculty development modules:** Structured training sessions that help instructors understand their classroom demographics, recognize their own cultural perspectives and potential biases, and develop strategies for inclusive pedagogy (Kressler & Kressler, 2020). These modules would be designed to be discipline-specific to address the unique challenges in STEM fields.
3. **Inclusive assessment practices:** Diversification of assessment methods to include collaborative projects, oral presentations, and authentic assessments that allow students to demonstrate knowledge in culturally meaningful ways (Hammond, 2014; Leary et al., 2020).
4. **Student voice mechanisms:** Regular opportunities for students to provide feedback on course content relevance and to suggest examples or applications from their own cultural contexts (Paris, 2012; Paris & Alim, 2017).

Figure 2. Conjecture Map

Explanation:

- By infusing the course content with culturally relevant examples and perspectives, students will be more likely to identify with the course material and the instructor, which might result in more successful students who remain within the STEM field.
- By implementing culturally responsive pedagogy within the course, instructors would be more informed on how to serve their student population (Ladson-Billings, 1995).
- This could also inform future faculty development in terms of implementing culturally responsive pedagogy within the STEM courses (Leary et al., 2020; Kressler & Kressler, 2020).
- Maintenance of culturally sustaining pedagogy (Paris, 2012).

Immediate and Long-Term Goals

The immediate objectives of this design-based research include raising awareness of culturally responsive pedagogy across STEM departments and deepening scholarly understanding of equity-minded instructional practices within disciplinary contexts. The long-term goal is to institutionalize culturally responsive pedagogy as a foundational element of STEM curriculum design, creating sustainable systemic change that enhances educational equity and student success across the institution.

To gradually implement the goals into action, I will be dividing the process into four phases. Each of the stakeholders will be tasked to begin with self-reflection. In this phase, instructors will participate in a training and educational effort to better understand their individual classroom's demographic makeup. The second phase will focus on the actual curriculum design, where the instructors, along with potentially students, will be able to review and adjust the syllabus to align with a culturally competent model provided to them. Through this process, the stakeholders will be able to instill cultural relevance and adjust the learning outcomes accordingly. The third phase will focus on the problems of practice and have a hands-on approach. Instructors will be encouraged to incorporate student-driven projects and emphasize the importance of inclusive communication. Most importantly, this phase will also require regular feedback mechanisms to foster engagement from both sides. The final phase will focus on continuous improvement and will provide insight into student retention and engagement.

Lastly, each phase will be enriched by emphasizing the importance of faculty collaboration, as this can result in positive sharing of knowledge as well as partnership building with the community and industry to support culturally responsive teaching

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